

Examination of Teacher Candidates' Social Media Addictions and Academic Procrastination Behaviors According to Various Variables

Assist. Prof. Dr. Mustafa Ersoy
(ORCID: 0000-0002-7320-8844)
Cumhuriyet University

Assist. Prof. Dr. İlhami Arseven
(ORCID: 0000-0001-9750-5862)
Cumhuriyet University

Abstract

This study examined pre-service teachers' social media addiction and academic procrastination behaviors according to various variables. The study used survey model as a research model. The participants were 171 teacher candidates studying at Sivas Cumhuriyet University Faculty of Education. The results of the study indicated no significant difference between the academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates and their gender, years of undergraduate education, social media membership status, frequencies of social media usage, years of social media usage, times spent on social media, and environments they were in to connect to social media. No significant difference was found between social media addiction levels of teacher candidates and environments they were in to connect to social media and their social media usage years. However, while the mean scores of male teacher candidates in the "conflict" sub-dimension of the SMAS were significantly higher than the mean scores of female teacher candidates, there was no significant difference in other sub-dimensions according to their gender. Again, in the "conflict" sub-dimension of the social media addiction scale, the mean scores of the second year teacher candidates were significantly higher than the fourth year students. While the mean scores of the teacher candidates with social media accounts in the "occupation" sub-dimension of the SMAS were significantly higher than those who did not have a social media account, there was no significant difference between their social media addiction levels in other sub-dimensions and their social media membership status. In addition, the study determined that those who used social media more than once a day had higher addiction levels in the "occupation" sub-dimension of SMAS compared to those who used social media once a day and more than once a week, and addiction levels differed according to the time they spent on social media. The results indicated that there was a low level, positive and statistically significant relationship between the APBS scores of the teacher candidates and the scores they got from the whole SMAS and other sub-dimensions of it except for the "mood modification" sub-dimension. The findings were interpreted and discussed based on the relevant literature.

Key words: Social media addiction; academic procrastination behaviors; teacher candidates

**E-Uluslararası
Pedagogji Dergisi**

**Cilt: 1, Sayı: 1, 2021
ss. 87-105**

**Makale türü:
Araştırma makalesi**

**Received: 03.03.2021
Accepted: 19.04.2021**

Suggested Citation

Ersoy, M. and Arseven, İ. (2021). Examination of teacher candidates' social media addictions and academic procrastination behaviors according to various variables. *E-International Journal of Pedagogji (E-IJPA)*, 1(1), 87-107. Doi: <https://trdoi.org/10.27579808/e-ijpa.31>

INTRODUCTION

Despite the lightness given by individuality in the transition process from sociality to "social-virtuality", one of the types of communication that has been transferred from daily life to the internet environment, especially in countries with strong social ties to meet the need for sociality, is communication through social media. People have tended to use social media tools for a longer period of time due to the auxiliary elements they offer such as likes, pokes and comments, as well as communication. These symbolic reinforcers, which can be considered among the needs of the era, are designed to stay in the system as long as they influence individuals, and they are put into service with updates to make individuals feel better using that platform. This situation starts to replace the real life of some individuals and turns into addiction. Cheung (2011), as cited by [Teyfur, Akpunar, Safali and Ercengiz \(2016\)](#) states that the pleasure gained through using social media can encourage strong and frequent use habits, and this forms a prerequisite for addiction. Byun et al. (2009) (cited in [Gürültülü, 2016](#), p.28) define addiction as "getting used to the substance that causes emotional, mental or physiological reactions and the inability to control one's own impulses at the point of quitting or applying an action". [Tutgun-Ünal \(2015, p.93\)](#), as cited by [Çelik \(2017\)](#), defines social media addiction, which is a type of addiction, as " a psychological problem that develops with cognitive, affective and behavioural processes, and causes problems such as occupation, mood modification, relapse and conflict in many areas of daily life, such as private life, business life, academic life and social life." However, this situation can go so far that it does not hesitate to show its effects in various areas of life. The increasing variety of social media tools can be among the various reasons for this situation. According to Mayfield (2008), social media is "a platform where users can easily participate, create and share content, and it includes social networks, wikis, blogs and virtual worlds" (cited in [Gürültülü, 2016](#), 8). This diversity leads people to spend their whole days on these platforms without realizing it and to procrastinate their most important tasks. [Gürültülü \(2016\)](#) underlines that the increase in the time allocated for social media and networks has become an important factor in the emergence of social media addiction and has become an important predictor of procrastination behaviour. [Turkish Language Association \(2018\)](#) defines the word procrastination as "postponement, adjournment, suspension, deferment". In the literature, several definitions of procrastination can be found. As [Can \(2018\)](#) cites, Haycock, McCarty and Skay (1998) use the term procrastination to refer to "voluntarily delaying a planned task, although the result is known to be worse due to the delay, failure of self-regulation", [Knaus \(2002\)](#) defines it as "a problematic habit that causes an individual to postpone a task, which needs to be done on time and with priority, to another time for no valid reason", it is defined by [Milgram, Mey-Tal and Levison \(1998\)](#) to mean "avoiding the implementation of an intention", Schouwenburg et al. (2004) define it as "putting off a task that can be done today until tomorrow", [Solomon and Rothblum \(1984\)](#) define it as "the act of delaying tasks unnecessarily in a way that will cause subjective discomfort", it is used by [Steel \(2007\)](#) to refer to "failure to do things on time and postponement of responsibilities, decisions or duties that need to be done", and [Van Erde \(2000\)](#) defines it as "a characteristic or a behavioural tendency to delay making a decision or doing a job". [Kağan \(2009\)](#) defines academic procrastination as "a problem seen in areas such as preparing for the exams, doing homework, attending meetings and completing projects with academic advisors".

[Teyfur, Akpunar, Safali and Ercengiz \(2016\)](#) found that participants with social media accounts were more busy with social media, social media usage time was a factor affecting occupation, social media occupation increased as the social media usage time increased, the frequency of social media usage was a factor affecting occupation, social media occupation increased as the frequency of social media usage increased, and social media usage time did not affect the level of academic procrastination. [Gürültülü \(2016\)](#) found that social media

addiction is a significant predictor of academic procrastination behaviour. His findings indicated that social media addiction explained approximately 19% of academic procrastination behaviour. Demir (2017) found a moderate and positive relationship between internet addiction and academic procrastination.

In addition to "Do faculty of education students' social media addiction levels and academic procrastination behaviors differ according to different variables?" and "Is there a significant relationship between faculty of education students' social media addiction levels and academic procrastination behaviors?" questions, the researchers collected data to answer the following questions:

1. Do teacher candidates' social media addiction and academic procrastination behaviors differ according to their gender, years of undergraduate education, social media membership status, frequencies of using social media platforms, social media usage years, environments they were in to connect to social media and the average time they spend on social media?
2. Is there a relationship between teacher candidates' social media addiction and academic procrastination behaviors?

METHODOLOGY

Since this study aimed to examine the social media addiction levels and academic procrastination behaviors of university students without any intervention, the study used survey methods, which are among the frequently used methods in quantitative research. Among the survey models, the study used general survey and correlational survey models. Correlational survey models are a research model that aims to determine the existence and/or degree of change between two or more variables (Karasar, 2000). The study used the survey model because it aimed to investigate social media addiction and academic procrastination behaviors based on personal views and statements.

Participants

The participants were determined on a voluntary basis using convenience sampling method from among the teacher candidates studying at Sivas Cumhuriyet University Faculty of Education. Information about the students participating in this study is shown in Table 1.

Data Collection Tools

The study used the "Social Media Addiction Scale (SMAS)", which was developed by Tutgun-Ünal and Deniz (2015). This scale, which consists of 41 items in the 5-point Likert-type (never corresponds to 1, rarely corresponds to 2, occasionally corresponds to 3, often corresponds to 4 and always corresponds to 5), has four sub-factors; namely, occupation ($\alpha = .932$), mood modification ($\alpha = .892$), relapse ($\alpha = .914$), and conflict ($\alpha = .958$). These factors explain 59% of the total variance. Tutgun-Ünal and Deniz (2015) reported the internal consistency coefficient of the scale as $\alpha = .967$. This study reported the internal consistency coefficient of the scale as $\alpha = .955$.

Another scale used in the study was the "Academic Procrastination Behaviour Scale (APBS)", and Çakıcı (2003) reported the reliability value of this scale as $\alpha = .92$. "Academic Procrastination Scale", which was developed to measure whether high school and university students postpone academic tasks such as studying, doing homework, preparing projects, and preparing for exams, is a 5-point Likert type (it does not reflect me at all corresponds to 1, it reflects me very little corresponds to 2, it reflects me a little corresponds to 3, it mostly reflects

me corresponds to 4, and it reflects me completely corresponds to 5) which includes 19 items. Participants can get the highest score of 95 and the lowest of 19 from the scale, which consists of 12 positive and 7 negative statements, and the higher the score is, the higher the academic procrastination tendency is (Çakıcı, 2003). This study reported the internal consistency coefficient of the scale as $\alpha = .701$.

Table 1. Students' demographic information

Variable		n	%
Years of undergraduate education	First year	31	18,12
	Second year	15	8,77
	Third year	66	38,59
	Fourth year	59	34,50
SM account	Yes	134	78,36
	No	37	21,64
SM usage years	Between one and three years	38	22,22
	Between four and six years	48	28,07
	More than six years	85	49,71
Frequency of using SM	Once a day	16	9,36
	More than once a day	141	82,45
	Several times a week	14	8,19
Gender	Female	122	71,35
	Male	49	28,65
Average time spent on SM	Between five and 30 minutes	83	48,54
	Between 31 and 60 minutes	47	27,48
	More than 60 minutes	41	23,98
The environment to connect SM	Home	74	43,27
	Anywhere with a wireless network	62	36,26
	Other	35	20,47

The researchers developed a "Personal Information Form" to reveal the demographic information of the teacher candidates and the variables within the scope of the study. The form included demographic information of teacher candidates, such as their gender, years of undergraduate education, social media membership status, social media usage time.

Data Collection

The researchers obtained data by applying it to students, who voluntarily participated in the study, of Sivas Cumhuriyet University Faculty of Education in the classroom environment in the 2018-2019 academic year. The forms consisting of the social media addiction scale and the academic procrastination scale were given to the participants. The researchers made necessary explanations before application. It took approximately 20 minutes for the participants to answer the forms.

Data Analysis

The study used SPSS15.0 in statistical analysis of the data. Within the scope of the first sub-problem of the study, the study used the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test to determine whether the collected data showed normal distribution. To determine whether there is a significant difference between groups in data with normal distribution ($p < .05$), the study conducted t-test in bivariate cases, and ANOVA test in cases with more than two variables. In cases where the ANOVA test was used and there was a significant difference between the groups, the study first examined the homogeneity of the variances and determined that the variances were homogeneous. Afterwards, the study used the Scheffé Test to determine the difference between the groups. The study used Kruskal Wallis Test, one of the non-parametric tests, for the data that violated normality assumptions in cases with more than two variables. In cases where the Kruskal Wallis Test was used and there was a significant difference between the

groups, the study first examined the homogeneity of the variances and determined that the variances were homogeneous, and the study used Scheffee Test as a post hoc test to determine the differences between the groups. The study used Pearson's correlation test to analyze the data collected for the second sub-problem of the study.

FINDINGS

This section includes findings obtained in line with the aims of the research.

Findings Regarding the First Sub-Problem

1. Findings regarding the relationship between social media addiction of education faculty students and the gender variable

The results regarding whether the levels social media addiction of the teacher candidates differed according to the gender variable are given in Table 2.

Table 2. T-Test Results Regarding the Relationship between Social Media Addiction Scores and the Gender Variable

Subscale	Gender	n	X	ss	sd	t	p
Occupation	Female	122	2,82	.87	169	.69	.49
	Male	49	2,71	.89			
Mood Modification	Female	122	2,48	.86	169	-1.26	.21
	Male	49	2,67	.88			
Relapse	Female	122	2,32	.97	169	-.66	.51
	Male	49	2,42	.90			
Conflict	Female	122	2,03	.77	169	-2.87	.01*
	Male	49	2,42	.86			

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

Table 2 indicated that there was no significant difference between the social media addiction levels of teacher candidates and the gender variable in the sub-dimensions of occupation, mood modification, and relapse ($p > .05$). However, the results indicated a significant difference between the mean scores of the male and female teacher candidates in the conflict sub-dimension of the scale. The mean scores of the male teacher candidates in the "conflict" sub-dimension of the SMAS was 2.42, and the mean scores of the female teacher candidates was 2.03. Therefore, in this sub-dimension of the scale, the mean scores of the male teacher candidates were significantly higher than the mean scores of the female teacher candidates.

2. Findings regarding the relationship between teacher candidates' social media addiction and the years of undergraduate education variable

The results regarding whether the social media addiction of the teacher candidates differed according to years of undergraduate education are presented in Table 3 in the sub-factors.

The Kruskal Wallis-H test indicated no significant difference ($p > .05$) between the social media addiction of teacher candidates and years of undergraduate education variable in the sub-dimensions of occupation, mood modification, and relapse. However, it indicated a significant difference in the conflict sub-dimension ($\chi^2 = .40$; $sd = 3$; $p < .05$). The results of the post-hoc Scheffee test conducted in order to determine the difference for the conflict sub-factor are given in Table 4.

Table 3. Kruskal Wallis-H Test Results Regarding the Relationship between Social Media Addiction Scores and the Years of Undergraduate Education Variable

Factor	Years of Undergraduate Education	N	X sira	x ²	sd	p
Occupation	First year	31	79.06	5.97	3	.113
	Second year	15	91.00			
	Third year	66	96.61			
	Fourth year	59	76.50			
	Total	171				
Mood Modification	First year	31	79.06	5.97	3	.113
	Second year	15	91.00			
	Third year	66	96.61			
	Fourth year	59	76.50			
	Total	171				
Relapse	First year	31	78.95	5.06	3	.168
	Second year	15	111.10			
	Third year	66	87.59			
	Fourth year	59	81.54			
	Total	171				
Conflict	First year	31	91.13	8.40	3	.038*
	Second year	15	114.77			
	Third year	66	86.98			
	Fourth year	59	74.89			
	Total	171				

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

Table 4. Post Hoc Scheffee Test Results Conducted to Determine among which Groups Social Media Addiction Scores Differed according to the Years of Undergraduate Education Variable

Factor	Year(s) of Undergraduate Education (i)	Years of Undergraduate Education (j)	X, ~Xj	Sh x	P
Conflict	Second year	First year	.406	.253	.464
		Third year	.486	.230	.220
		Fourth year	.682	.232	.038*

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

Table 4 indicated a significant difference between the mean scores of the second grade teacher candidates and the fourth grade teacher candidates in the "conflict" sub-dimension of SMAS. The mean scores of the second grade teacher candidates in the "conflict" sub-dimension of the SMAS was 2.63, and the mean scores of those studying in the fourth grade was 1.95. Therefore, in this sub-dimension of the scale, the mean scores of the second grade teacher candidates were significantly higher than the mean scores of the fourth grade teacher candidates.

3. Findings regarding the relationship between teacher candidates' social media addiction and their social media membership status

The results regarding whether the social media addiction of the teacher candidates differed according to their social media membership status are given in Table 5.

Table 5. T-Test Results Regarding the Relationship between Social Media Addiction Scores and the Social Media Membership Status Variable

Factor	Membership	n	X	ss	sd	t	p
Occupation	Yes	134	2,87	.85	169	2.48	.01*
	No	37	2,48	.93			
Mood Modification	Yes	134	2,55	.90	169	.58	.56
	No	37	2,45	.75			
Relapse	Yes	134	2,33	.95	169	-.60	.54
	No	37	2,43	.96			
Conflict	Yes	134	2,08	.80	169	-1.73	.09
	No	37	2,35	.86			

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

Table 5 indicated no significant difference between the social media addiction levels of teacher candidates and their social media membership status in the mood modification, relapse, and conflict sub-dimensions ($p > .05$). However, in the occupation sub-dimension of the scale, the results indicated a significant difference between the mean scores of the students with and without social media accounts. The mean scores of the teacher candidates with social media accounts in the "occupation" sub-dimension of the SMAS was 2.87, and the mean scores of the teacher candidates without social media accounts was 2.48. Therefore, in this sub-dimension of the scale, the mean scores of the teacher candidates with social media accounts were significantly higher than the mean scores of those without social media accounts.

4. Findings regarding the relationship between teacher candidates' social media addiction and their frequencies of social media usage

The results regarding whether the social media addiction of teacher candidates differed according to their frequencies of social media usage are given in Table 6.

Table 6. Kruskal Wallis-H Test Results Regarding the Relationship between Social Media Addiction Scores and the Frequency of Social Media Usage Variable

Factor	Frequency of Usage	N	X sira	χ^2	Sd	p
Occupation	Once a day	16	62.44	12	2	.003*
	More than once a day	141	91.96			
	Several times a week	14	52.86			
	Total	171	76.50			
Mood Modification	Once a day	16	82.22	2.3	2	.317
	More than once a day	141	88.24			
	Several times a week	14	67.75			
	Total	171	76.50			
Relapse	Once a day	16	65.19	8.9	2	.011
	More than once a day	141	91.28			
	Several times a week	14	57.86			
	Total	171	76.50			
Conflict	Once a day	16	69.59	3.9	2	.14
	More than once a day	141	88.43			
	Several times a week	14	70.21			
	Total	171	76.50			

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

Table 6 indicated no significant difference between the social media addiction levels of teacher candidates and their social media membership status in the mood modification, relapse and conflict sub-dimensions ($p > .05$). However, there was a significant difference the social media addiction levels of teacher candidates and their social media membership status in the occupation ($\chi^2 = 12$; $sd. = 2$; $p < .05$) sub-dimension. The results of the post hoc Scheffee test conducted to determine the differences among the groups for the occupation sub-factor are given in Table 7.

Table 7. Post Hoc Scheffee Test Results Conducted to Determine among which Groups Social Media Addiction Scores Differed according to the Frequency of Social Media Usage Variable

Factor	Frequency of Usage (i)	Frequency of Usage (j)	$X_i - X_j$	Sh x	p
Occupation	More than once a day	Once a day	.566	.223	.042*
		Several times a week	.749	.223	.004*
	Once a day	More than once a week	-.566	.223	.042*
		Several times a week	.182	.299	.831

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

Table 7 indicated that there were significant differences between the mean scores of the teachers candidates who used social media more than once a day and once a day and several times a week in the "occupation" sub-dimension of SMAS. In the "occupation" sub-dimension of the SMAS, the mean scores of the teacher candidates who used social media more than once

a day was 2.91, the mean scores of those who used social media once a day was 2.34, and the mean scores of those who used social media several times a week was 2.16. Therefore, in this sub-dimension of the scale, the mean scores of the teacher candidates who used social media more than once every day was significantly higher than the mean scores of those who used social media once every day and several times a week.

5. Findings regarding the relationship between teacher candidates' social media addiction and the environment participants were in to connect to social media

The results regarding whether the teachers candidates' social media addiction differed according to the environment they were in to connect to social media are presented in Table 8 in sub-scales.

Table 8. ANOVA Test Results Regarding the Relationship between Social Media Addiction Scores and the Environments Participants were in to Connect to Social Media

Factor	The environment they were in to	n	X	ss	Var. K.	KT	Sd	KO	F	p		
Engagement	Home	74	2.76	.88	Between-groups	1.28	2	.64				
	Anywhere with a wireless network	62	2.73	.77		130.46	168	.77			.82	
	Other	35	2.96	1.05	Total		131.74	170				
	Total	171	2.79	.88								
Mood Modification	Home	74	2.51	.86	Between-groups	1.95	2	.97				
	Anywhere with a wireless network	62	2.45	.76		Within-groups	127.49	168			.76	1.28
	Other	35	2.74	1.06	Total		129.44	170				
	Total	171	2.53	.87								
Relapse	Home	74	2.30	.95	Between-groups	.43	2	.21				
	Anywhere with a wireless network	62	2.41	.89		Within-groups	153.92	168			.92	.23
	Other	35	2.35	1.07	Total		154.35	170				
	Total	171	2.35	.95								
Conflict	Home	74	2.06	.78	Between-groups	2.29	2	1.15				
	Anywhere with a wireless network	62	2.11	.83		Within-groups	111.65	168			.67	1.72
	Other	35	2.37	.87	Total		113.94	170				
	Total	171	2.14	.82								

*Statistically significant at p < .05 level.

Table 8 indicated no significant difference between the social media addiction levels of teacher candidates and environments they were in to connect to social media in the occupation, mood modification, relapse and conflict sub-dimensions (p > .05).

6. Findings regarding the relationship between teacher candidates' social media addiction and their social media usage years.

The results regarding whether the social media addiction of the teacher candidates differed according to their social media usage years are given in Table 9 in sub-scales.

Table 9. ANOVA Test Results Regarding the Relationship between the Participants' Social Media Addiction Scores and Their Social Media Usage Years

Factor	Year(s)	n	X	Ss	Var.K.	KT	Sd	KO	F	p
Occupation	Between one and three years	38	2.93	.86	Between-groups	2.16	2	1.08	1.40	.249
	Between four and six years	48	2.88	.91		Within-groups	129.58	168		
	More than six years	85	2.68	.87	Total		131.74	170		
	Total	171	2.79	.88						
Mood Modification	Between one and three years	38	2.78	.93	Between-groups	3.28	2	1.64	2.18	.116
	Between four and six years	48	2.53	.92		Within-groups	126.17	168		
	More than six years	85	2.43	.81	Total		129.44	170		
	Total	171	2.53	.87						
Relapse	Between one and three years	38	2.54	.89	Between-groups	2.17	2	1.08	1.20	.305
	Between four and six years	48	2.37	1.08		Within-groups	152.18	168		
	More than six years	85	2.25	.90	Total		154.35	170		
	Total	171	2.35	.95						
Conflict	Between one and three years	38	2.22	.76	Between-groups	2.68	2	1.34	2.02	.135
	Between four and six years	48	2.30	.87		Within-groups	111.26	168		
	More than six years	85	2.02	.81	Total		113.94	170		
	Total	171	2.14	.82						

*Statistically significant at p < .05 level.

The results of the ANOVA test indicated no significant difference between the social media addiction sub-factors and social media usage years ($p > .05$).

7. Findings regarding the relationship between teacher candidates' social media addiction and the time they spent on social media

The results regarding whether the social media addiction of the teacher candidates differed according to the time they spent on social media are given in Table 10.

Table 10. ANOVA Test Results Regarding the Relationship between Social Media Addiction Scores and the Time Spent on Social Media Variable

Factor	Time Spent on Social Media	n	X	Ss	Var. K.	KT	Sd	KO	F	p
Occupation	Between five and 30 minutes	83	2.58	.81	Between-groups	10.46	2	5.23	7.24	.001*
	Between 31 and 60 minutes	47	2.80	.80	Within-groups	121.28	168		.72	
	More than 60 minutes	41	3.20	.97						
	Total	171	2.79	.88	Total	131.74	170			
Mood Modification	Between five and 30 minutes	83	2.36	.80	Between-groups	11.89	2	5.94	8.49	.000*
	Between 31 and 60 minutes	47	2.43	.81	Within-groups	117.56	168		.70	
	More than 60 minutes	41	3.00	.94						
	Total	171	2.53	.87	Total	129.44	170			
Relapse	Between five and 30 minutes	83	2.14	.91	Between-groups	12.52	2	6.26	7.42	.001*
	Between 31 and 60 minutes	47	2.31	.76	Within-groups	141.81	168		.84	
	More than 60 minutes	41	2.81	1.09						
	Total	171	2.35	.95	Total	154.34	170			
Conflict	Between five and 30 minutes	83	1.94	.79	Between-groups	16.80	2	8.40	14.5	.000*
	Between 31 and 60 minutes	47	2.01	.73	Within-groups	97.14	168		.58	
	More than 60 minutes	41	2.70	.74						
	Total	171	2.14	.82	Total	113.94	170			

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

The results indicated significant differences between social media addiction scores and the time spent on social media in all sub-dimensions ($p < .05$). The results of the post hoc Scheffee test conducted to determine between which groups the differences occurred for each sub-factor are given in Table 11.

Table 11. Post Hoc Scheffee Test Results Conducted to Determine among which Groups Social Media Addiction Scores Differed according to the Time Spent on Social Media

Factor	Average Time(i)	Average Time(j)	X, ~Xj	Sh x	P
Occupation	Between five and 30 minutes	Between five and 30 minutes	-.22	.16	.352
		More than 60 minutes	-.62	.16	.001*
	Between 31 and 60 minutes	Between five and 30 minutes	-.22	.16	.352
		More than 60 minutes	-.39	.18	.100
	More than 60 minutes	Between five and 30 minutes	.62	.16	.001*
		Between 31 and 60 minutes	.39	.18	.100
Mood Modification	Between five and 30 minutes	Between five and 30 minutes	-.07	.15	.905
		More than 60 minutes	-.64	.16	.000*
	Between 31 and 60 minutes	Between five and 30 minutes	.07	.15	.905
		More than 60 minutes	-.57	.18	.007*
	More than 60 minutes	Between five and 30 minutes	.64	.16	.000*
		Between 31 and 60 minutes	.57	.18	.007*
Relapse	Between five and 30 minutes	Between five and 30 minutes	-.16	.17	.620
		More than 60 minutes	-.67	.18	.001*
	Between 31 and 60 minutes	Between five and 30 minutes	.16	.17	.620
		More than 60 minutes	-.51	.20	.037*
	More than 60 minutes	Between five and 30 minutes	.67	.18	.001*
		Between 31 and 60 minutes	.51	.20	.037*
Conflict	Between five and 30 minutes	Between five and 30 minutes	-.06	.14	.898
		More than 60 minutes	-.75	.15	.000*
	Between 31 and 60 minutes	Between five and 30 minutes	.06	.14	.898
		More than 60 minutes	-.69	.16	.000*
	More than 60 minutes	Between five and 30 minutes	.75	.15	.000*
		Between 31 and 60 minutes	.69	.16	.000*

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

The results indicated a significant difference in the occupation factor between the group that spent between five and 30 minutes and the group that spent more than 60 minutes on social media according to the average time spent on social media platforms ($p < .05$).

In the mood modification factor, there were significant differences between the group who spent between five and 30 minutes and the group who spent more than 60 minutes, and the group who spent who spent between 31 and 60 minutes and the group who spent more than 60 minutes ($p < .05$).

In the relapse factor, there were significant differences between the group who spent between five and 30 minutes and the group who spent more than 60 minutes, and the group who spent between 31 and 60 minutes and the group who spent more than 60 minutes ($p < .05$).

In the conflict factor, there were significant differences between the group who spent between five and 30 minutes and the group who spent more than 60 minutes, and the group who spent between 31 and 60 minutes and the group who spent more than 60 minutes or ($p < .05$).

8. Findings regarding the relationship between academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates and the gender variable

The results regarding whether the academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates differed according to the gender variable are given in Table 12.

Table 12. T-Test Results Regarding the Relationship between Academic Procrastination Behaviour Scores According and the Gender Variable

Factor	Gender	n	\bar{X}_{ort}	ss	sd	t	p
Academic Procrastination Behaviour	Female	122	2,98	.64	169	-.64	.522
	Male	49	3.05	.69			

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

The results indicated no significant difference between academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates and the gender variable ($p > .05$).

9. Findings regarding the relationship between the teacher candidates' academic procrastination behaviors and the years of undergraduate education variable

The results regarding whether the academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates differed according to years of undergraduate education are given in Table 13.

Table 13. Kruskal Wallis-H Test Results Regarding the Relationship between Academic Procrastination Behaviour Scores and the Years of Undergraduate Education Variable

Factor	Years of	N	X	χ^2	sd	p
Academic Procrastination Behaviour	First year	31	81.19	.798	3	.850
	Second year	15	79.77			
	Third year	66	86.79			
	Fourth year	59	89.23			
	Total	171				

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

The results indicated no significant difference between academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates and their years of undergraduate education ($p > .05$).

10. Findings regarding the relationship between academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates and their social media membership status

The results regarding whether the academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates differed according to their social media membership status are given in Table 14.

Table 14. T-Test Results Regarding the Relationship between Academic Procrastination Behaviour Scores and the Social Media Membership Status Variable

Factor	Account	n	X_{ort}	ss	sd	t	p
Academic Procrastination Behaviour	Yes	134	3.03	.61	169	.96	.338
	No	37	2.91	.79			

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

The results indicated no significant difference between academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates and their social media membership status ($p > .05$).

11. Findings regarding the relationship between the teacher candidates' academic procrastination behaviors and their frequencies of social media usage

The results regarding whether teacher candidates' academic procrastination behaviors differed according to their frequencies of social media usage are given in Table 15.

Table 15. Kruskal Wallis-H Test Results Regarding the Differentiation of Academic Procrastination Behaviour Scores According to Frequencies of Social Media Usage

Score	Frequency	N	X	χ^2	sd	p
Academic Procrastination Behaviour	Once a day	16	68.66	.343	2	.180
	More than once a day	141	89.20			
	Several times a week	14	73.64			
	Total	171				

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

The results indicated no significant difference between academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates and their frequencies of social media usage ($p > .05$).

12. Findings regarding the relationship between the teacher candidates' academic procrastination behaviors and their social media usage years

The results regarding whether the academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates differed according to their social media usage years are given in Table 16.

Table 16. ANOVA Test Results Regarding the Differentiation of Academic Procrastination Behaviour Scores According to the Social Media Usage Years

Score	Year(s)	n	X	ss	Var. K.	KT	Sd	KO	F	P
Academic Procrastination Behaviour	Between one	38	2.92	.56	Between-groups	1.57	2	.78	1.87	.157
	Between for and	48	3.15	.66						
	More than six	85	2.95	.68	Total	72.04	170			
	Total	171	3.00	.65						

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

As it can be understood from Table 16, variances were homogeneous since the p value was above .05. The ANOVA test, which was conducted to determine whether the academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates differed significantly according to the social media usage years variable, yielded no significant difference between the arithmetic means of the groups ($p > .05$).

13. Findings regarding the relationship between academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates and the time they spent on social media platforms

The results regarding whether the academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates differed according to the average time they spent on social media platforms are given in Table 17.

Table 17. ANOVA Test Results Regarding the Differentiation of Academic Procrastination Behaviour Scores According to the Time Spent on Social Media Platforms

Score	Time	n	X	ss	Var. K.	KT	Sd	KO	F	P
Academic Procrastination Behaviour	Between five and	83	2.99	.60	Between-groups	.04	2		.02	
	Between 31 and 60	47	3.02	.75	Within-groups	72.00	168	.43	.04	.958
	More than 60	41	3.01	.63	Total	72.04	170			
	Total	171	3.00	.65						

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

As it can be understood from Table 17, variances were homogeneous since the p value was above .05. The ANOVA test, which was conducted to determine whether the academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates differed significantly according to the time they spent on social media platforms, yielded no significant difference between the arithmetic means of the groups ($p > .05$).

14. Findings regarding the relationship between the teacher candidates' academic procrastination behaviors and the environment they were in to connect to social media

The results regarding whether the academic procrastination behaviors of the teacher candidates differed according to the environment they were in to connect to social media are presented in Table 18 and Table 19.

Table 18. ANOVA Test Results Regarding the Differentiation of Academic Procrastination Behaviour Scores According to the Environments Participants were in to Connect to Social Media

Score	Environment	n	X	ss	Var.K.	KT	Sd	KO	F	p
Academic Procrastination Behaviour	Home	74	3.07	.63	Between-groups	2.90	2	1.5		
	Anywhere with a	62	2.83	.70	Within-groups	69.14	168	.41	3.53	.032*
	Other	35	3.15	.55	Total	72.04	170			
	Total	171	3.00	.65						

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

The results indicated a significant difference between the means of the groups ($p < .05$). Since there was a significant difference, a post hoc Scheffee test was conducted to determine the differences between the groups. The results of the post hoc Scheffee test are given in Table 19.

Table 19. Post Hoc Scheffee Test Results Conducted to Determine among which Groups Academic Procrastination Behaviors Scores Differed according to the Environments Participants were in to Connect to Social Media Platforms

	Environments	Environments	X, ~Xj	Sh x	p
Academic Procrastination Behaviour	Anywhere with a wireless network	Home	-.156	.077	.133
		Other	-.270	.093	.017*

*Statistically significant at $p < .05$ level.

The results indicated a significant difference between the mean scores of the teacher candidates who used social media in anywhere with a wireless network and those who used social media in other environments. While the mean scores in the APBS of the teacher candidates who connected to social media from anywhere with a wireless network were 2.86, the mean scores of those who connected to social media from other environments were 3.13.

Therefore, the mean scores of the teacher candidates who connected to social media from other environments were significantly higher than the mean scores of those who connected from anywhere with a wireless network.

Findings Regarding the Second Sub-Problem

1. Findings regarding the relationship between the teacher candidates' scores from the occupation sub-dimension of social media addiction scale and their academic procrastination behaviors

Table 20. Pearson's Correlation Analysis Results Regarding the Teacher Candidates' Scores from the Sub-Dimensions of Social Media Addiction Scale (SMAS) and Academic Procrastination Scale (APS)

Sub-Dimensions of the Social Media Addiction Scale	Occupation	Mood Modification	Conflict	Relapse	Whole Social Media Addiction Scale
Academic Procrastination Scale	.244**	.148	.269**	.200**	.284**

N=178; p < .05*; p < .01**

The results indicated low level of positive and significant correlations between the participants' scores from the "occupation" sub-dimension of the Social Media Addiction Scale and their scores from the Academic Procrastination Scale ($r = .244$), between their scores from the "conflict" sub-dimension of the Social Media Addiction Scale and their scores from the Academic Procrastination Scale ($r = .269$), between their scores from the "relapse" sub-dimension of the Social Media Addiction Scale and their scores from the Academic Procrastination Scale ($r = .200$), and between their scores from the whole Social Media Addiction Scale and their scores from the Academic Procrastination Scale ($r = .284$). Therefore, it can be concluded that as the social media addiction of the candidates increased, their academic procrastination behaviors increased at a low significance level. However, no significant relationship was found between the teacher candidates' scores from the "mood modification" sub-dimension of the Social Media Addiction Scale and their scores from the Academic Procrastination Scale.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study investigated various variables such as the social media addiction levels and academic procrastination behaviors of teacher candidates, gender, years of undergraduate education, social media membership status, frequency of using social media platforms, years of social media usage, environments they were in to connect to social media and the average time spent on social media by examining whether there were significant differences between variables, and determined whether there was a relationship between social media addiction and academic procrastination. The study determined a significant relationship between social media addiction of the participants and the gender variable in the "conflict" sub-dimension; however, there was no significant difference in other sub-dimensions with respect to the gender variable. The results revealed that social media addiction levels of male teacher candidates were higher than those of female teacher candidates in the "conflict" sub-dimension. This confirms previous findings in the literature [Esen, 2010](#); [Tanrıverdi and Sağır, 2014](#); [Tutgun-Ünal and Deniz 2016](#); [Özdemir, 2019](#)). Conflict sub-dimension measures the effect of social media on creating negative consequences in a person's life ([Tutgun-Ünal and Deniz, 2016](#)). In this vein, it can be said that male teacher candidates used social media more, although it had a negative effect on their daily lives. This situation brings along the possibility of not being able to finish the job they started, neglecting people in their social

lives, and falling behind in their work productivities compared to women ([Tutgun-Ünal and Deniz, 2016](#)).

The study determined a significant relationship between social media addiction of the participants and the years of undergraduate education variable in the "conflict" sub-dimension; however, there was no significant difference in other sub-dimensions with respect to the years of undergraduate education variable. This finding is in line with those of [Tutgun-Ünal \(2015\)](#) and [Gürültülü \(2016\)](#), since they found no significant difference between social media addiction and the years of undergraduate education variable. Our research failed to account for the age variable; therefore, the researchers believe that the significant difference in the conflict sub-dimension might had been caused by the age variable rather than the years of undergraduate education variable. This study determined that the mean scores of the second year teacher candidates in the "conflict" sub-dimension were significantly higher than the fourth year teacher candidates. Various studies ([Tutgun-Ünal, 2015](#); [Tutgun-Ünal and Deniz, 2016](#); [Çayırılı, 2017](#); [Özdemir, 2019](#); [Yüksel, Çini and Yasak, 2020](#)) confirm that social media addiction decreases as the age increases. Despite the lack of the age variable, we believe that our findings regarding the years of undergraduate education variable compare well with the aforementioned studies.

The study determined a significant relationship between social media addiction of the participants and the social media membership status variable in the "occupation" sub-dimension; however, there was no significant difference in other sub-dimensions with respect to the social media membership status variable. The results revealed that the social media addiction levels of teacher candidates with social media accounts were higher than those without a social media account in the "occupation" sub-dimension. [Teyfur et al. \(2017\)](#) determined that in the "occupation" sub-dimension, the mean scores of the teacher candidates with social media accounts were higher than those without a social media account not, and their findings are consistent with the current research findings. In this vein, [Tutgun-Ünal and Deniz \(2016\)](#) argue that teacher candidates with social media accounts are deeply occupied with social media than those without a social media account, they think more about what is happening on social media, and the issue of entering and being connected to social media constantly keeps their minds busy.

The study determined a significant relationship between social media addiction of the participants and the frequency of social media usage variable in the "occupation" sub-dimension; however, there was no significant difference in other sub-dimensions with respect to the frequency of social media usage variable. The results revealed that the social media addiction levels of teacher candidates who used social media more than once a day were higher than those who use social media once a day and several times a week in the "occupation" sub-dimension. [Coşar \(2019\)](#) and [Teyfur et al. \(2017\)](#) found that teacher candidates who used social media more than once a day had higher levels of social media addiction compared to those who used once a day and several times a week. The current findings confirm previous findings in the literature. Therefore, as [Tutgun-Ünal and Deniz \(2016\)](#) discuss, it can be stated that teacher candidates who use social media more than once a day are deeply occupied with social media think more about what is happening on social media, and entering and being connected to social media constantly keeps their minds preoccupied compared to those who use social media less.

The study determined no significant relationship between the social media addiction of the participants and the environments participants were in to connect to social media in all sub-dimensions. This finding is consistent with the findings of [Durdu \(2019\)](#)'s study, which investigated the relationship between the level of social media addiction and the environments participants were in to connect to social media. In addition, this study determined no significant relationship between the social media addiction of the participants and the social media usage years in all sub-dimensions. This finding is consistent with the findings of the study conducted by [Teyfur et al. \(2017\)](#), except for the "occupation" sub-dimension. In this regard, it can be concluded that the

environments participants are in to connect to social media and the years of social media usage are not determining variables in the level of social media addiction.

The study determined significant relationships between social media addiction of the participants and the time spent on social media variable in all sub-dimensions. This difference is between the participants who used social media "between five and 30 minutes" and those who used it "more than 60 minutes" and in favour of those who used "more than 60 minutes" in all sub-dimensions. In addition, the study determined significant differences between those who used social "between 31 and 60 minutes" and those who used it "more than 60 minutes" in favour of those who used it "more than 60 minutes" in all sub-dimensions except for the "occupation" sub-dimension. In other words, teacher candidates who spent longer time on social media had higher addiction levels compared to those who spent less time. In this vein, it can be said that as the time spent on social media increases, the level of addiction increases. [Şentürk \(2017\)](#) underlines that social media addiction increases as the time spent on social media increases. It can be said that the excessive duration of the behaviour in addictive behaviour is an important variable.

The study determined no significant difference between academic procrastination behaviors of the participants and the following six variables: the gender, the years of undergraduate education, the social media membership status, the years of social media usage, the frequency of social media usage, and the time spent on social media. [Coşar \(2017\)](#) found that no significant difference between academic procrastination behaviors of teacher candidates and the years of undergraduate education, social media membership status, years of social media usage and frequency of social media usage, and the present findings are consistent with her findings. Therefore, it can be concluded that these variables are not determinant variables in academic procrastination behaviors. The study determined a significant relationship between academic procrastination behaviors of the participants and the environments they were in to connect to social media. The academic procrastination behaviour levels of those who were in other environments were higher than those who were anywhere with a wireless network.

The study determined a low level positive correlation between the mean scores of the participants from the APBS and the mean scores they got from SMAS, except for the mood modification sub-dimension. Various studies have found a positive and statistically significant relationship between social media addiction and academic procrastination behaviour ([Ergenç, 2011](#); [Gürültülü, 2016](#); [Coşar, 2019](#); [Teyfur et al., 2017](#); [Durdu, 2019](#)), and these findings are consistent with the current research findings. In this vein, we can say that as the level of social media addiction increases, academic procrastination increases at a low level. Considering that the results of the study indicated a statistically significant relationship, albeit low, between social media addiction and academic procrastination, the following statements can be put forward:

- ✓ The school counselling services should raise parents' and students' awareness's on the effects of social media addiction not only on academic procrastination but also on learning and academic achievement.
- ✓ The issues of social media addiction and its relationship with academic procrastination should be included in school and classroom counselling programs, and children should be made aware on this issue from early ages.
- ✓ Parent education should be intensified to lower students' social media addiction and academic procrastination behaviors.

Öğretmen Adayların Sosyal Medya Bağımlılığı Ve Akademik Erteleme Davranışlarının Çeşitli Değişkenlere Göre İncelenmesi

Dr. Öğrt.Üyesi Mustafa Ersoy
(ORCID: 0000-0002-7320-8844)
Cumhuriyet Üniversitesi

Dr. Öğrt.Üyesi İlhami Arseven
(ORCID: 0000-0001-9750-5862)
Cumhuriyet Üniversitesi

Özet

Bu çalışma, üniversite öğrencilerinin sosyal medya bağımlılığı ve akademik erteleme davranışlarının incelenmesinin amaçlandığı nicel bir araştırmadır. Araştırmanın evrenini Sivas Cumhuriyet Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesinde öğrenim gören öğretmen adayları oluştururken, araştırmacının çalışma grubunu 171 öğretmen adayı oluşturmaktadır. Veriler; Tutgun, Ünal ve Deniz (2015) tarafından geliştirilen "Sosyal Medya Bağımlılığı Ölçeği (SMBÖ)" ve Çakıcı (2003) tarafından geliştirilen "Akademik Erteleme Davranışı Ölçeği (AEDÖ)" ile toplanmıştır. Ayrıca çalışma grubunda yer alan öğretmen adaylarının kişisel niteliklerini ortaya koymak amacıyla araştırmacılar tarafından geliştirilen "Kişisel Bilgi Formu" kullanılmıştır. Öğretmen adaylarının akademik erteleme davranışlarında cinsiyet, öğrenim gördükleri sınıf, sosyal medya üyelik durumları, sosyal medya kullanım sıklıkları, sosyal medya kullanım yılı, sosyal medyada harcanan süre ve sosyal medyaya bağlanılan ortama göre anlamlı bir fark bulunamamıştır. Öğretmen adaylarının sosyal medya bağımlılık düzeylerinde; sosyal medyaya bağlanma ortamına ve sosyal medya kullanım yılına göre anlamlı bir fark yoktur. Bununla birlikte SMBÖ "çatışma" alt boyutunda erkek öğretmen adaylarının aldıkları puanların ortalamaları, kız öğretmen adaylarının puan ortalamalarından anlamlı derecede yüksek çıkarken diğer alt boyutlarda cinsiyete göre bir farklılık bulunmamaktadır. Öğretmen adaylarının AEDÖ puanları ile "duygu durum düzenleme" alt boyutu haricinde SMBÖ ölçeğinin tamamı ve diğer alt boyutlarından aldıkları puanlar arasında düşük düzeyde, pozitif yönlü ve istatistiksel olarak anlamlı ilişki olduğu ortaya çıkmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sosyal media bağımlılığı, akademik erteleme davranışı, öğretmen adayları

**E-Uluslararası
Pedandragoji Dergisi**

**Cilt: 1, Sayı: 1, 2021
ss. 87-105**

**Makale türü:
Araştırma makalesi**

102

Gönderi Tarihi: 03.03.2021
Kabul Tarihi: 19.03..2021

Suggested Citation

Ersoy, M. and Arseven, İ. (2021). Öğretmen Adayların Sosyal Medya Bağımlılığı Ve Akademik Erteleme Davranışlarının Çeşitli Değişkenlere Göre İncelenmesi *E-Uluslararası Pedandragoji Dergisi (E-UPAD)*, 1(1), 87-105. <https://trdoi.org/10.27579808/e-ijpa.31>

GENİŞLETİLMİŞ ÖZET

Problem: Sosyal media, iletişimin yanı sıra beğeni, dürtme, yorum gibi standart haline gelmeye başlayan yardımcı unsurlar nedeniyle sosyal media araçlarını daha uzun süreli kullanmaya yönelmiştir. Bu durum bazı bireylerde birçok gerçek yaşam durumunun önüne geçmeye başlayarak bağımlılığa dönüşmektedir. Bu çeşitlilik sayesinde kişi farkında olmadan gününün tamamını bu mecrada geçirmeye ve çoğu önemli görevi ertelemeye yönelmiştir. Gürültü'ye (2016) göre sosyal medya bağımlılığının ortaya çıkmasında sosyal medya ve ağlara ayrılan zamandaki artışlar önemli bir faktör haline gelerek erteleme davranışının önemli bir yordayıcısı olmuştur. Bu araştırma öğretmen adaylarının sosyal medya bağımlılık düzeyleri ve akademik erteleme davranışlarının cinsiyet, sınıf düzeyi, sosyal medya üyelik durumu, sosyal medya uygulamalarını kullanım sıklığı, sosyal medya kullanım süresi (yıl), sosyal medyaya bağlanılan ortam ve sosyal medyaya girildiğinde harcanılan ortalama süre gibi çeşitli değişkenler açısından incelenerek, anlamlı bir farklılık gösterip göstermediğinin incelenmesi ve sosyal medya bağımlılığı ile akademik erteleme davranışı arasında bir ilişkinin olup olmadığını belirlemek amacıyla yapılmıştır.

Yöntem: Bu çalışmada, üniversite öğrencilerinin sosyal medya bağımlılığı ve akademik erteleme davranışları herhangi bir müdahale olmaksızın incelenmesi amaçlandığı için nicel araştırmalarda sıklıkla kullanılan tarama yöntemlerinden yararlanılmıştır. Tarama modellerinden genel tarama ve ilişkisel tarama modelleri bir arada kullanılmıştır. İlişkisel tarama modeli, iki veya daha fazla değişken arasındaki değişimin varlığını ve / veya derecesini belirlemeyi amaçlayan bir araştırma modelidir (Karasar, 2000). Araştırmanın evrenini Sivas Cumhuriyet Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesinde öğrenim gören öğretmen adayları oluştururken, araştırmanın çalışma grubunu 171 öğretmen adayı oluşturmaktadır. Veriler; Tutgun, Ünal ve Deniz (2015) tarafından geliştirilen "Sosyal Medya Bağımlılığı Ölçeği (SMBÖ)" ve Çakıcı (2003) tarafından geliştirilen "Akademik Erteleme Davranışı Ölçeği (AEDÖ)" ile toplanmıştır. Ayrıca çalışma grubunda yer alan öğretmen adaylarının kişisel niteliklerini ortaya koymak amacıyla araştırmacılar tarafından geliştirilen "Kişisel Bilgi Formu" kullanılmıştır.

Bulgular: Araştırmanın sonunda; öğretmen adaylarının akademik erteleme davranışlarında cinsiyet, öğrenim gördükleri sınıf, sosyal medya üyelik durumları, sosyal medya kullanım sıklıkları, sosyal medya kullanım yılı, sosyal medyada harcanan süre ve sosyal medyaya bağlanılan ortama göre anlamlı bir fark bulunamamıştır. Öğretmen adaylarının sosyal medya bağımlılık düzeylerinde; sosyal medyaya bağlanma ortamına ve sosyal medya kullanım yılına göre anlamlı bir fark yoktur. Bununla birlikte SMBÖ "çatışma" alt boyutunda erkek öğretmen adaylarının aldıkları puanların ortalamaları, kız öğretmen adaylarının puan ortalamalarından anlamlı derecede yüksek çıkarken diğer alt boyutlarda cinsiyete göre bir farklılık bulunmamaktadır. Yine Sosyal medya bağımlılığı ölçeğinin "çatışma" alt boyutunda ikinci sınıfta öğrenim gören öğretmen adaylarının aldıkları puanların ortalamaları, dördüncü sınıfta öğrenim gören öğrencilere göre anlamlı derecede yüksek çıkarken diğer alt boyutlarda öğrenim görülen sınıfa göre sosyal medya bağımlılık düzeylerinde anlamlı bir fark bulunmamıştır. Sosyal medya üyeliği bulunan öğretmen adaylarının SMBÖ "meşguliyet" alt boyutundaki puanlarının ortalamaları, üye olmayanlara göre anlamlı derecede yüksek çıkarken diğer alt boyutlarda sosyal medya üyeliğine göre sosyal medya bağımlılık düzeylerinde anlamlı bir fark bulunmamıştır. Ayrıca SMBÖ "meşguliyet" alt boyutunda sosyal medyayı her gün bir defadan fazla kullananların, her gün bir defa ve haftada birden fazla kullananlara göre bağımlılıklarının daha yüksek olduğu ve sosyal medyada harcanan süreye göre de bağımlılığın farklılaştığı belirlenmiştir. Öğretmen adaylarının AEDÖ puanları ile "duygu durum düzenleme" alt boyutu harcinde SMBÖ ölçeğinin tamamı ve diğer alt boyutlarından aldıkları puanlar arasında düşük düzeyde, pozitif yönlü ve istatistiksel olarak anlamlı ilişki olduğu ortaya çıkmıştır.

Sonuç ve Tartışma: Elde edilen bulgular literatüre dayalı olarak yorumlanmış ve tartışılmıştır. Sonuçlar "çatışma" alt boyutunda erkek öğretmen adaylarının sosyal medya bağımlılık düzeylerinin kız öğretmen adaylarına göre daha fazla olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Bu bulgu Esen (2010), Tanrıverdi ve Sağır (2014), Tutgun-Ünal ve Deniz (2016) ve Özdemir (2019) tarafından yapılan araştırma bulguları ile uyumludur. Çatışma alt boyutu, sosyal medyanın kişinin yaşamında olumsuz sonuçları oluşturma etkisini ölçmektedir (Tutgun-Ünal ve Deniz, 2016) Bu noktada erkek öğretmen adaylarının gündelik yaşamlarında olumsuz bir etki oluşturmalarına rağmen sosyal medyayı daha fazla kullandıkları söylenebilir. Bu durum erkek öğretmen adayları için başladıkları işi bitirememeye, sosyal hayatlarında yer alan kişileri ihmal etme, iş üretkenliklerinde düşme risklerinin kadınlara göre daha yüksek olma ihtimalini beraberinde getirmektedir (Tutgun-Ünal ve Deniz, 2016). u çalışmada ikinci sınıfta öğrenim gören öğretmen adaylarının "çatışma" alt boyutunda aldıkları puanların ortalamaları, dördüncü sınıftakilere göre anlamlı derecede yüksek çıkmıştır. Yapılan bazı araştırmalarda (Tutgun-Ünal, 2015; Tutgun-Ünal ve Deniz, 2016; Çayırılı, 2017; Özdemir, 2019; Yüksel, Çini ve Yasak, 2020) yaş arttıkça sosyal medya bağımlılığının azaldığını göstermektedir. Bu sonucun, ikinci sınıfta öğrenim gören öğretmen adaylarının "çatışma" alt boyutundaki puan ortalamalarının dördüncü sınıftakilere göre yüksek çıkmasını açıklayabileceği düşünülmektedir. Sosyal medya bağımlılığı ile akademik erteleme davranışı arasında pozitif yönlü ve istatistiksel olarak anlamlı ilişki olduğu belirlenmiş olup, bu bulgular mevcut araştırma bulgularıyla uyumludur. Buna göre sosyala medya bağımlılık düzeyi arttıkça, akademik erteleme davranışında da düşük düzeyde bir artışın olduğu görülmektedir.

Öneriler: Sosyal medya bağımlılığının sadece akademik erteleme davranışlarına değil, bunun yanısıra öğrenmeye ve akademik başarıya etkisi konusunda aileler ve öğrenciler okul rehberlik servisleri tarafından bilinçlendirilmelidir. Sosyal medya bağımlılığı konusu ve akademik erteleme davranışıyla ilişkisi, okul ve sınıf rehberlik programlarında yer almalı, küçük yaşlardan itibaren çocuklara bu konuda bilinç kazandırılmalıdır. Ayrıca öğrencilerin sosyal medya bağımlılıkları ve akademik erteleme davranışlarını alt seviyelere indirmek için anne-baba eğitimleri yoğunlaştırılmalıdır.

REFERENCES

- Can, S. (2018). *Academic Procrastination Behaviors, Internet Addiction, and Basic Psychological Needs of Adolescents: A Model Proposal*. Master Thesis, Yıldız Technical University, İstanbul.
- Coşar, H. A. (2019). *Examination the Relationship Between Teacher Candidates' Social Media Addiction and Academic Performance*. Master Thesis, Aksaray University, Aksaray.
- Çayırılı, E. (2017). *The Relationship Between the Characteristics of Social Media Usage and Personality Structures, Life Satisfaction and Depression*. Master Thesis, Işık University, İstanbul.
- Çelik, M. (2017). Examination of the Level of Dependency on Social Media College Students: A Study on Students of İstanbul Kültür University. *1st International Conference on New Trends in Communication. İstanbul*.
- Demir, Y. (2017). *Relationships Among Internet Addiction, Academic Motivation, Academic Procrastination, and School Attachment in Adolescents*. PhD. Thesis, İnönü University, Malatya.

- Durdu, A. (2019). *An Investigation of Social Media Addiction and Academic Procrastination of 7th and 8th Grade Students in the Second School*. Master Thesis, Toros University, Mersin.
- Ergenç, A. (2011). *Web 2.0 and Virtual Socialization: Example of Facebook*. Master Thesis, Maltepe University, İstanbul.
- Esen, E. (2010). *An Investigation of Psycho-Social Variables in Predicting Internet Addiction Among Adolescents*. Master Thesis, Dokuz Eylül University, İzmir.
- Gürültülü, E. (2016). *Analysis of the Relationship Between High School Students' Social Media Addictions and Academic Delaying Behaviors*. Master Thesis, Marmara University, İstanbul.
- Kağan, M. (2009). Determining the Variables which Explain the Behavior of Academic Procrastination in University Students. *Ankara University Faculty of Educational Sciences Journal*, 42(2), 113-128.
- Karasar, N. (2000). Scientific Research Method. *Ankara: Nobel*.
- Özdemir, Z. (2019). Social Media Addiction among University Students. *Journal of Beykoz Academy*, 7 (2), 91-105.
- Şentürk, E. (2017). *Comparison of Social Media Addiction Between Depression, Anxiety Disorder, Mixed Anxiety Depressive Disorder Patients, Control Group and Assessing the Relationship Between Social Media Addiction and Personality Traits of Users*. Specialty Thesis, Gazi University, Ankara.
- Teyfur, M., Akpunar, B., Safali, S., ve Ercengiz, M. (2017). An Examination of the Relationship between Academic Procrastination Behavior and Social Media Dependency of the Faculty of Education Students in terms of Different Variables. *Turkish Studies International Periodical for the Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic*, 12 (33), 625-640.
- Tanrıverdi, H. ve Sağır, S. (2014). The Impact of High School Students' Intentions in the Use of Social Media and the Way of Their Adoption of Social Media on Their Success. *Adıyaman University Journal of Social Sciences Institute*, 7(18), 775-822.
- Tutgun-Ünal, A. (2015). *Social Media Addiction: A Research on University Students*. PhD Thesis, Marmara University, İstanbul.
- Tutgun-Ünal, A., Deniz, L. (2016). An Investigation of Social Media Addiction of University Students. *Route Educational and Social Science Journal*, 3 (2), 155-181.
- Turkish Language Association. (2018). Türkçe Sözlük. *Ankara: Türk Dil Kurumu Yayınları*.
- Yüksel, M.Y., Çini, A., Yasak, B. (2020). Investigation of Social Media Addiction, Loneliness and Life Satisfaction in Young Adults. *Atatürk University Journal of Kazım Karabekir Education Faculty*, 40, 66-85.